

On-stage cell scanner

These files contain the design and instructions for fabricating the on-stage cell scanner used in the manuscript “Imaging vs non-imaging Raman spectroscopy for high-throughput single-cell phenotyping” by Hobro et al, submitted to Analytical Chemistry.

Print the STL files using ABS or any other suitable filament. There are 4 parts:

- Main brace x1
- Dish holder x1
- Speaker cone brace x2

Using two small speakers as transducers, attach to the main brace with glue, as shown in the photo. It may be helpful to attach only one at a time, using gravity to maintain the position, until the glue dries, then attach the other one.

The dish holder is designed to hold in the 35mm plastic, glass-bottom, or quartz-bottom dish.

The two small speakers used in our manuscript were: UXCELL XLYD43, 40hm, 3W, and the small amplifier was taken from a generic battery powered portable speaker. The speaker dimensions of importance are whether it can fit into the main brace as follows:

After connecting the amplifier, the included audio (.mp3) file can be played through the system. It contains two frequencies, one in each channel, which are not harmonics of each other (59Hz and 79Hz), causing the system to eventually trace out a scan pattern which is approximately the following:

The actual size of the scan pattern at the sample plane is then controllable by the amplitude of the speaker, which is controlled by the volume of the amplifier.

The total travel of the dish only needs to be on the order of several micrometers, which is too small to see by eye, but can be best judged by looking at a small point in a sample, and then switching on the dual frequency signal. The resulting motion blur shows the effective size of the scan pattern.

Care should be taken not to cause undue vibration on the stage by excessive amplification. At a stage scan amplitude in the order of 5 micrometers, the scanner was stable in our experiments, and no unwanted vibration was detected in our system. When testing at significantly higher volumes, it was possible to feel and hear vibration.

It is also possible to play other sound files through the sample scanner to study the effects of different music on the cell growth, though this was not done in our study.